

A STUDY ON THE CORRELATION OF AUTOFRETTAGE PRESSURE WITH CYCLING LIFE OF TYPE3 COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSEL

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1 Introduction

Type3 cylinder is a composite pressure vessel fully over-wrapped with carbon/epoxy composite layers over an aluminum liner, which is the most ideal and safe high pressure vessel due to the lightweight and the leak-before-burst characteristics [1-2].

At the end of manufacturing process of Type3 cylinder, the autofrettage process is applied for the purpose of improving fatigue life, where the cylinder is once over pressurized to a certain pressure usually beyond its test pressure and yield limit of aluminum liner [3]. This process induces compressive residual stress on the liner when it goes back to zero pressure, resulting in noticeable improvement in cycling life of the cylinder [4-7]. Therefore, autofrettage pressure has a close correlation with cycling life of Type3 cylinder.

In this study, structural analysis and cycling test for a typical Type 3 cylinder were extensively conducted to establish optimum autofrettage pressure which gives maximum cycling life and favorable failure mode.

2 Approach

Because the liner stresses determine cycling life of Type3 cylinder, a path-dependent nonlinear finite element analysis for the cylinder was conducted to determine liner stresses accurately due to plastic deformation of aluminum liner in autofrettage process. And then, the maximum principal strain of liner derived from the finite element analysis was taken into the σ - ϵ curve to change into stress. And the stress was taken into the S-N curve of liner material to predict cycling life in different level of autofrettage pressure. This prediction results were compared with cycling test.

3 Finite element analysis

3.1 Analysis technique and sequence

This cylinder is a SCBA composite pressure vessel which has 24.0 MPa service pressure and 6.80 liter of volume (Fig.1). Fig.2 shows the dimension of the cylinder: layer thicknesses are 2.41 mm for liner and 4.60 mm for composites in cylindrical part. Since the Type3 cylinder is a cyclic symmetry structure due to helical layer, only a part of a central angle of whole body is modeled and cyclic symmetry condition is applied as shown in Fig.3. And internal pressure is loaded by constant pressure on the inner surface of liner. ABAQUS program is used for finite element analysis and a quadratic displacement element of three dimensions which has orthotropic stiffness is applied.

To evaluate an influence of compressive residual stress induced by autofrettage process, a path-dependent analysis procedure should be applied as shown in Fig.4. Aluminum is assumed in elastic-perfectly plastic materials for constitutive equation.

3.2 Stress analysis results and calculation of strain amplitude

3.2.1 Stress analysis results

The effect of autofrettage pressure was examined in the range of 105% to 195% of test pressure increasing by 5%. The results were classified into three types according to failure mode and cycling life. For the first, Fig.5 and 6 show compressive residual stress and maximum principal strain distribution of liner in the range of 105% to 115%. Next, Fig.7 and 8 show results of the range of 120% to 155%. Finally, Fig.9 and 10 show results of range of 160% to 195%. Location of maximum principal strain generated by each autofrettage pressure is also an expected leak part of the cylinder.

3.2.2 Calculation of strain amplitude

It is assumed that fatigue life of aluminum liner is determined by strain amplitude from zero pressure to test pressure. The strain amplitude is obtained from stress analysis results of cylinder using equation (1) at the location where maximum strain occurs.

$$\Delta\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{test\ pressure} - \varepsilon_{zero\ pressure} \quad (1)$$

3.3 Prediction and verification of cycling life

To predict cycling life of cylinder, we used the following procedure. Stress amplitude of liner was obtained from σ - ε curve and strain amplitude. The stress amplitude was taken into the S-N curve of liner material.

This prediction results were compared with cycling test.

3.3.1 Tensile test results of liner material

Tensile test of liner material was conducted to obtain σ - ε curve. A specimen was made from liner, and test was conducted according to ASTM-E08. The results are shown in Fig.11.

3.3.2 Fatigue test results of liner material

Fatigue test of liner material was conducted to obtain S-N curve. A specimen was made from liner, and stress ratio was 0.1. Test was conducted in range of 60% to 90% of yield strength considering stress level of liner material. The S-N curve for aluminum material generally has a linear in log scale as shown in Fig.12, and it is expressed as equation (2).

$$\sigma = m_1 N_f^{m_2} \quad (2)$$

From curve fitting of test results of liner material, m_1 and m_2 are 1262 and -0.16, respectively.

3.3.3 Prediction results of cycling life

In the analysis, the cycling life of cylinder increased according to an increase in autofrettage pressure up to 155 % of test pressure, but it began to slightly decrease above 160% as shown in Fig.13.

Failure location by leak was also changed from cylinder part to dome knuckle part in the range of 105 to 155 % pressure, and again from dome knuckle part to boss neck above 160%.

These phenomena could be properly explained by that the compressive residual stress induced by autofrettage pressure differs by locations, and it is the highest in the cylinder part and begins to decrease around the dome knuckle part and further decreases along dome contour up to the boss neck in sequence. Compressive residual stress at any location of liner increases with increase of autofrettage pressure, but only up to compressive yield limit of liner, and beyond that point further increasing of autofrettage pressure does not have any effect on cycling life of that location.

Consequently, the 155 % pressure was determined as an optimum autofrettage pressure which generates maximum residual stress in cylinder part and moderate residual stress in dome part, resulting in maximum cycling life and desirable failure location of dome knuckle part.

3.3.4 Verification test for cylinder

Cycling tests for several cylinders were also conducted to verify analysis results. Change of cycling life and failure locations in testing showed good agreement with analysis result in overall trend as shown in Fig.14 to 16.

4 Conclusions

In this study, structural analysis and cycling test for a typical Type 3 cylinder were extensively conducted to establish correlation autofrettage pressure with fatigue life. So, the 155 % pressure was determined as an optimum autofrettage pressure which generates maximum residual stress in cylinder part and moderate residual stress in dome part, resulting in maximum cycling life and desirable failure location of dome knuckle part.

Therefore, the analysis and testing results presented in this study can be used as a guideline to set up an optimum autofrettage pressure for general Type3 composite pressure vessels.

Fig.1. structural concept of Type3 cylinder

Fig.2. Cross section and dimensions of Type3 composite cylinder

Fig.3. Finite element modeling of Type3 composite cylinder

Fig.4. Loading sequence considering plastic deformation by autofrettage pressure of liner material

Fig.5. Compressive residual stress distribution of liner in zero pressure with 105 % autofrettage pressure

Fig.6. Maximum strain distribution of liner in test pressure with 105 % autofrettage pressure

Fig.8. Maximum strain distribution of liner in test pressure with 155 % autofrettage pressure

Fig.7. Compressive residual stress distribution of liner in zero pressure with 155 % autofrettage pressure

Fig.9. Compressive residual stress distribution of liner in zero pressure with 195 % autofrettage pressure

Fig.10. Maximum strain distribution of liner in test pressure with 195 % autofrettage pressure

Fig.11. Tensile test results of liner coupon specimen

Fig.12. Fatigue test results of liner coupon specimen

Fig.13. Change of cycling life along an increase of autofrettage pressure

Fig.14. Failure mode in cycling test with 105 % autofrettage pressure

Fig.15. Failure mode in cycling test with 155 % autofrettage pressure

Fig.16. Failure mode in cycling test with 195 % autofrettage pressure

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